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**Public Opinion in Antonio Gramsci and
Edward L. Bernays**
Bottom-Up Empowerment vs. Top-Down Management

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Introduction

“Ideas and opinions are not spontaneously ‘born’ in each individual brain: they have had a centre of formation, of irradiation, of dissemination, of persuasion [...] which has developed them and presented them in the political form of current reality.” (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 192-193)

A Marxist intellectual imprisoned by Mussolini’s Fascist regime, Antonio Gramsci in the 1930s wrote incisively about how societies secure the consent of the governed. In his *Prison Notebooks*, he observed that the state’s stability in his time rested not merely on coercion but on “[...] the active consent of those over whom it rules [...]” (Gramsci, 1971, p.244) – subtle ideological forces that prevented oppressed classes from revolting. Across the ideological divide, Edward L. Bernays – often dubbed the “father of public relations” – candidly described how modern democracies are governed by invisible mechanisms of persuasion (Tye, 1998). Despite stark differences in context and purpose, the two contemporaries sought to explain the centrality of public opinion in modern democracies. Each, in his own way, illuminated the paradox of democratic power: that public consensus can be orchestrated behind the scenes, whether through schools, churches, and newspapers or modern mass media and advertising.

This paper, therefore compares Gramsci’s and Bernays’s theories on public opinion¹, highlighting why such a comparison is illuminating. Despite emerging from opposing ideological traditions, both thinkers address the “engineering” of consent in democracies.² By examining their arguments in depth, this paper aims to show how elite influence over public opinion can be understood as both an instrument of social control and a tool of stable governance, depending on one’s perspective of democracy.

In what follows, Gramsci’s theory of hegemony will be analysed, then Bernays’s theory of propaganda, comparing how public opinion formation is conceptualised in each framework. In the last chapter, a synthesis of these insights will reveal the paradox that a democratic society’s stability often rests on techniques of influence that are not fully democratic. Although Gramsci and Bernays start from a similar diagnosis of power’s reliance on consent, they diverge in the conclusions they draw for public opinion’s role in democracy. Gramsci’s framework ultimately calls for radical democratic change, whereas Bernays seeks to stabilise elite rule in a minimalist democracy.

¹ For Gramsci, this is the nature of *hegemony* and *counter-hegemony*, for Bernays *propaganda*. It should be pointed out here that this work is decidedly centred on the two author’s discussions of public opinion as a political factor within their overlapping historical and societal context; capitalist liberal democracy.

² Bernays published *The Engineering of Consent* in 1947, describing in his own words “[...] action based only on thorough knowledge on the situation and on the application of scientific principles [...] to the task of getting people to support ideas and programs”. The phrase later gained prominence through the work of media critics Herman & Chomsky (1988), who described the mass media’s role in “manufacturing consent” in terms that resonate with both Gramsci’s and Bernays’s insights.

1 Gramsci's road to social change

Gramsci developed his theory of hegemony in the context of trying to explain a perplexing historical fact: the failure of socialist revolutions in Western Europe despite ripe conditions predicted by Marx. Observing the persistence of bourgeois rule, he argued that power rests on both coercion and cultural leadership.³

1.1 Violent Domination vs. Cultural Hegemony

While early Marxists often highlighted repression and coercion by armies and police (Kann, 1980), Gramsci (1971) claims that modern capitalist societies rely on more subtle methods of cultural leadership (p. 12). He observes that in Western Europe, the bourgeoisie proved resilient not simply by seizing power through coercion but by weaving its worldview into the very fabric of public opinion and moral life. According to Gramsci:

“The supremacy of a social group manifests itself in two ways, as ‘domination’ and as ‘intellectual and moral leadership’ [...] A social group can, and indeed must, already exercise ‘leadership’ before winning governmental power (this indeed is one of the principal conditions for the winning of such power)” (Gramsci, 1971, p.57)

He thus goes beyond coercion to introduce “hegemony”: the cultural and consensual facets of class dominance. Under “normal” conditions, coercion is minimal but remains in the background, while society appears to consent voluntarily (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 155-156). For Gramsci, this “[...] common sense is the very stuff of hegemony” (1971, pp.419-425). But how can “common sense” come about when “[...] there does not exist, historically, a way of seeing things and of acting which is equal for all men, no more or less” (Gramsci, 1971, p.352)? Gramsci responds:

“The ‘spontaneous’ consent [...] to the general direction imposed on social life by the dominant fundamental group [...] is caused by the prestige (and consequent confidence) which the dominant group enjoys because of its position and function in the world of production.” (Gramsci, 1971, p. 12)

In other words, the public's acquiescence to existing social arrangements of the time is not truly “spontaneous” but is historically cultivated by the ruling class's⁴ influence and its role in the economy⁵. Largely a top-down construct, this hegemonic consent is disseminated “for reasons of

³ Gramsci's observations reflect the struggles and changes in social conditions for socialism in his time. He observed that in the “developed western states” of the early 20th century, the bourgeoisie had managed to anchor its rule in a broad base of popular consent, by propagating values and “conceptions of the world” that justified the capitalist order as part of the natural social fabric (Adamson, 1980; Fontana, 2006).

⁴ The ruling class for Gramsci here is the liberal, democratic, capitalist class which seeks to maintain the status quo through “passive revolution” and hegemony.

⁵ Of course, noting that Gramsci is Marxist, this is emphasised.

state” across civil society – media, churches, schools.⁶ In effect, the “normal exercise of hegemony” is the key to the resilience of capitalist democracies to fundamental social change. Only when consent breaks down does the state resort more nakedly to coercion over consent (Gramsci, 1971, p.210).

Through *hegemony*, Gramsci provides an analytical breakdown of public opinion formation as a function of class power. Public opinion is seen as neither innate nor freely formed in a vacuum; it is the result of a continuous social process in which the hegemony of a ruling group guides and limits the ideas circulating in society. If so, it is likewise the arena in which subordinate classes must mobilise for transformative change.

1.2 Organic Intellectuals and the Possibility of Change

“Are all intellectuals an autonomous and independent social group, or does every social group have its own particular specialised category of intellectuals?” (Gramsci, 1971, p.5)

Following this question, Gramsci makes the case that ideas and leadership need not always come from above; they can rise up from below in direct challenge to dominant ideology. A key premise is that intellectual activity need not be exclusive to a privileged few. In fact, “[...] the notion of ‘the intellectuals’ as a distinct social category independent of class is a myth” (Gramsci, 1971, p.3). In a celebrated passage, he argues:

“There is no human activity from which every form of intellectual participation can be excluded: homo faber cannot be separated from homo sapiens. Each man, finally, outside his professional activity, carries on some form of intellectual activity, that is, he is a ‘philosopher’ [...] and therefore contributes to sustain a conception of the world or to modify it [...]” (Gramsci, 1971, p.9)

Hence, “all men are intellectuals” and “philosophers” (1971, p.9; p.323). They differ not in potential but in social function; everyone, in some capacity, either sustains or challenges the prevailing worldview. From this starting point, Gramsci redefines the role of the intellectual in social life. He draws a line between “traditional intellectuals,” who claim neutrality (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 354–355)⁷, and “organic intellectuals,” who arise from a specific social class to articulate its worldview. “Organic” intellectuals to Gramsci are not merely a mass base reliant on refugees from the bourgeois class⁸ – every “new class” generates its own organic intellectuals, “[...] which the new

⁶ Gramsci extensively discusses *civil society*, a realm in which “traditional intellectuals” shape and uphold “common sense” that includes the media, churches, schools, and a network of institutions that align the subordinate groups’ worldview with the dominant group’s own.

⁷ “Traditional intellectuals” are distinguished by their profession, such as academics, clerics, literati and so on.

⁸ Gramsci develops Lenin’s critique of Kautsky’s idea that the intellectuals in worker’s movements serve formal functions of providing the ideology to the mass base of workers who are not intellectuals; Both Gramsci’s counter-hegemony and Lenin’s theory of the vanguard party attempt to incorporate the masses into the ideological foundations of socialist movements (Kann, 1980).

class has brought into prominence [...]” as essential organisers of its project (Simon, 1982; Gramsci, 1971, p.5).⁹ They do not simply theorise; they coordinate the class struggle, educating and uniting disparate¹⁰ groups and reshaping “common sense”—the taken-for-granted beliefs—on behalf of the subordinate class. As Crehan (2002) observes, they “excavate and amplify” kernels of “good sense” that align with emancipatory goals, challenging myths that sustain oppression.

This long-term preparatory struggle, or “war of position,” stands in contrast to the rapid “war of maneuver” of a direct insurrection (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 229–239). It involves steadily occupying key positions in civil society – media, educational institutions, community groups – so that dominant ideology is undermined and new values take hold among the populace. Only when a significant portion of the public embraces this alternative vision can a decisive “war of maneuver” succeed. Public opinion thus becomes the principal battlefield: both the ruling bloc and the challengers seek to win hearts and minds and thus secure the consent of society for its leadership.¹¹

The idea of “organic intellectuals” highlights Gramsci’s rejection of narrow economic determinism. Workers do not unite solely by economic position; consciousness and solidarity must be actively built from within the class. A factory worker may not recognise her potential as an agent of change until fellow workers—functioning as intellectuals—link her daily struggles and “[...] the interests of the class which is yet still subaltern [...]” (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 201–204). Thus, Gramsci assigns a pivotal role to leadership from *within* the masses. At the same time:

“One must do away once and for all with the belief that the final victory is certain because of the existence of objective conditions, in the sense that these conditions necessarily produce the revolution” (Gramsci, 1971, p. 336)

Such caution underpins Gramsci’s stance on revolution. The political events in his time revealed that¹² even in economic crises, “a powerful system of fortresses and earthworks” (Gramsci,

⁹ It can be observed that the “organic” intellectuals which every new class creates alongside itself and elaborates in the course of its development, are for the most part “specialisations” of partial aspects of the primitive activity of the new social type which the new class has brought into prominence (Gramsci, 1971, p.)

¹⁰ Gramsci noted that “common sense” in any society is heterogeneous and often internally contradictory, containing fragments of both resigned acceptance and critical awareness (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 419–425). Laclau & Mouffe(2014) build upon the heterogeneity of the left wing to propose an “articulation” of shared and diversified elements.

¹¹ Education is a key term shared by both authors with differing usage and purpose. “Educating” the public, in Gramsci’s view, means assisting the public in realising the counter-hegemonic consent of their class. Meanwhile, for Bernays, “education” is primarily a means of orchestrating the public mind, ensuring social stability by shaping citizen attitudes to align with democracy’s purported goals (Bernays, 1938, pp. 124–125). Rather than nurturing critical autonomy, this form of “public education” harnesses strategic persuasion—what he calls “engineering consent”—to guide mass sentiment and neutralize the disruptive potential of unchecked emotions.

¹² This is particularly because in the “West”, there exists a proper relation between State and civil society, in which the formal institution is protected by “[...] a powerful system of fortresses and earthworks [...]” that create stability and resilience (Gramsci, 1971, p.238). While criticising past Marxist thought such as that of Rosa Luxemburg, he states that a “war of maneuver” that simply tries to storm the state when economic conditions are ample would find itself to be “[...] out and out historical mysticism, the awaiting of a sort of miraculous illumination” (Gramsci, 1971, p.233).

1971, p. 238) protects the state, so a direct “war of maneuver” may be mere “[...] out and out historical mysticism [...]” (Gramsci, 1971, p. 233) if cultural groundwork is missing. Ruling blocs can also enact “passive revolution”¹³—superficial reforms from above—to neutralise opposition without truly redistributing power (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 105–114). This top-down adaptiveness reinforces Gramsci’s critique of determinism; even economic turbulence often leads to superficial adjustments rather than an automatic revolutionary upheaval. Economic conditions may “[...] create a terrain more favourable to the dissemination of certain modes of thought [...]”, but cultural foundations must be laid long before any seizure of state power (Gramsci, 1971, p. 57).

For Gramsci, a war of position is not a passive waiting game because “[...] a society does not set itself tasks for whose solution the necessary conditions have not already been incubated [...]” (Gramsci, 1971, p.106). Instead, change requires what he terms “trenchant patience” – the ability to persistently chip away at the dominant ideology and gradually mobilise¹⁴ public opinion favorable to change. To this end, the counter-hegemonic project requires consent as much as hegemony does. It is with this nuanced view that Gramsci writes:

“I am a pessimist because of intelligence, but an optimist because of will.” (Gramsci, 1994, p. 175)¹⁵

In the next chapter, Bernays’s top-down approach to public opinion and his emphasis on social order will be explored in relation to Gramsci’s bottom-up approach.

2 Bernays’s toolkit for social management

While Gramsci treated public opinion as the battleground for emancipatory social change, Edward L. Bernays saw it as a phenomenon to be skillfully managed to preserve social order and prevent disruptions. Bernays’s recognition of public opinion as central to modern society partly

¹³ Also phrased “revolution-restoration”, Gramsci initially derived this idea from Italian history – notably the case of the Italian *Risorgimento* (unification) in the 19th century, which he saw as a conservative-led unification that sidestepped mass democratic mobilization (Morton, 2007). Ruling blocs, in moments of crisis, enact limited reforms from above to co-opt popular demands and thus “renovate” their leadership without fundamental social change (Gramsci, 1971, pp.105-114).

¹⁴ “A human mass does not ‘distinguish’ itself, does not become independent ‘for itself’, without, in a broad sense, organising itself; and there is no organisation without intellectuals [...]” (Gramsci, 1971, p. 12)

¹⁵ “Pessimism of the intellect, optimism of the will” is a phrase closely associated with Gramsci, though he credits it to French writer Romain Rolland. Gramsci used it in a 1920s article and in a prison letter (1929) to his brother. The slogan captures Gramsci’s balance of sober analysis and revolutionary determination—indeed, true counter-hegemony involves an emotional mobilisation from below, not just a cerebral shift. This stance was Gramsci’s antidote to both fatalism and naive utopianism. It also reflected his lived experience: even as a prisoner in diminishing health, he maintained intellectual rigor in studying why past revolutions failed (intellectual pessimism about easy victory), yet he did not renounce the goal of emancipation (volitional optimism that struggles could eventually succeed). In the context of this paper, this motto underscores the difference from Bernays’ approach – Bernays was arguably an optimist of the intellect in the sense of believing he had the techniques to solve society’s problems, but a pessimist of the will regarding the public (assuming the masses could not rise to political wisdom). Gramsci’s motto, by contrast, encourages continually working for change despite grim conditions.

echoes Gramsci's but diverges starkly in intent.

2.1 Propaganda as a Democratic Necessity

“the engineering of consent is the very essence of the democratic process – the freedom to persuade and suggest” (Bernays, 1947, p.113, emphasis added)

Similar to Gramsci's focus on consent, Bernays draws on Walter Lippmann's claim that “[...] the significant revolution of modern times is [...] the revolution in the art of creating consent among the governed” (Lippmann, 1922, as cited in Bernays, 1923, p. 49). Lippmann had noted that news media selectively shape facts, compelling organised groups to employ press agents (Lippmann, 1922, p. 342). Rather than lamenting this, Bernays justifies it. Citing his practice as putting Lippmann's theory into action¹⁶, he states:

“The conscious and intelligent manipulation of the organized habits and opinions of the masses is an important element in democratic society. Those who manipulate this unseen mechanism of society constitute an invisible government which is the true ruling power of our country” (Bernays, 1928, p.37)

Bernays thus regards manipulation as a normal feature of democracy rather than its corruption. Because the average citizen cannot process all information, propaganda becomes a “regular organ of popular government” (Bernays, 1923, p. 38)—a practical stand-in for the unattainable ideal of a fully informed populace. He contends that top-down persuasion provides “freedom” to both rulers and the ruled, noting that “we have voluntarily agreed to let an invisible government sift the data [...] so that our field of choice shall be narrowed to practical proportions” (Bernays, 1928, p. 50). By invoking liberal democratic ideals¹⁷ even as he subverts them, Bernays transforms Lippmann's “radical critique into an apology for PR,” making “propaganda” synonymous with the proper management of public affairs (Jansen, 2013). To understand how Bernays elevates a specific elite to this role, we turn to the “intelligent few” as moral architects of public opinion.

2.2 Propaganda, PR Specialists, and the “Spectator” Democracy

¹⁶ Walter Lippmann's concept of the public as a “spectator” rather than a participant is central to the elitist theory of democracy that Bernays followed. In *The Phantom Public*, Lippmann (1925) wrote: “The public must be put in its place [so that] each of us may live free of the trampling and the roar of a bewildered herd.” While Bernays did not use such vivid language in *Propaganda*, he echoed the sentiment that average citizens (the “bewildered herd” in Lippmann's term) need guidance from a stable governing class. These views were shaped by disillusionment with mass opinion after World War I and the rise of mass media. Interestingly, Lippmann's ideas on “spectator democracy” and elite guidance were in part reactions to the same phenomena that Gramsci was analysing from the left: the unpredictability of mass politics, the sway of ideology, and the failure of rational public discourse. But where Gramsci saw a challenge to elevate the masses, Lippmann saw a reason to manage them more firmly. Bernays took elite theories and molded them into concrete PR practice, presenting the PR counsel as part-scientist, part-moral tutor for society.

¹⁷ For broader moral and ethical implications of Bernays's Public Relations theory see: Matern, S. (2023). *Edward L. Bernays' Propagandatheorie: Vom Kampf um Wirklichkeiten und Emotionen in der liberalen Demokratie*. Verlag Barbara Budrich; Bivins, T. H. (2013). A golden opportunity? Edward Bernays and the dilemma of ethics. *American Journalism*, 30(4), 496-519.

Bernays consistently frames propaganda as value-neutral—“a perfectly legitimate form of human activity” (1928, p. 20) – whose ethical dimension depends on “[...] the merit of the cause urged [...]” (1928, p. 20). Used properly, it channels mass energies toward “socially constructive” ends (Bernays, 1928, p. 53). He celebrates the “stability” achieved through such top-down influence.

Drawing on Lippmann’s elitist view of conferring advanced intellectual qualities to a select minority (Stoker, 2014), Bernays asserts that “[...] only through the active energy of the *intelligent few* can the public at large become aware of and act upon *new ideas*” (1928, p. 31, emphasis added). Here, Bernays recasts the “few” as active conduits of progress. Although this idea parallels Gramsci’s concept of “organic intellectuals” who emerge as societal conditions change, Bernays’s elites are not organically tied to any subaltern class but occupy a “higher” stratum. As he declares in *Crystallizing Public Opinion*, “The duty of the *higher strata* of society [...] is to *inject moral and spiritual*¹⁸ motives into public opinion” (Bernays, 1923, p. 217, emphasis added). Thus, while Gramsci imagines intellectual capacity emerging from lived experience, Bernays insists on formal expertise, suggesting that some, by virtue of their training, are especially suited to guide the masses with “[...] as nearly scientific an analysis as possible [...]” (Bernays, 1928, p. 97).

A key ambiguity in Bernays’s account is the moral dimension of PR specialists— he assumes a distinction between ethical and selfish uses of propaganda, yet he provides no mechanism to ensure the “invisible government” remains benevolent.¹⁹ Nonetheless, what is “good” to Bernays is preventing chaos²⁰ by taking on the burden of thinking for the public. This stance exemplifies what Westbrook (2005) calls “democratic realism” taken to the extreme: democracy is not rule *by* the people, but rule *for* the people by those who know better. The moral leadership Bernays attributes to PR experts is thus self-appointed. In *Speak up for democracy*²¹, Bernays writes:

“Democracy depends upon the participation, the voice, and the understanding of its citizens. Yet, in our modern mass society, that understanding must be organized if it is to be effective.” (Bernays, 1940, p.21)

Although Bernays references “participation” and “understanding,” he severely restricts them in

¹⁸ Bernays’s invocation of “moral and spiritual motives” reflects the Progressive Era belief that experts could uplift the irrational masses. In the chapter on ethical relations in *Crystallizing Public Opinion*, he quotes Ferdinand Tönnies to give this view academic weight. “It is certain that the power of public opinion is [...] more and more being influenced, changed, stirred, by impulses from below.” (Bernays, 1923, p.217).

¹⁹ In fact, history would soon provide examples of propaganda put to totalitarian ends. Bernays acknowledges that figures like Goebbels drew on his ideas, underscoring how easily “managing” public opinion can serve anti-democratic or oppressive agendas (Milburn, 2024).

²⁰ In fact, his emphasis on the necessity managing chaos for stability in democracy can be seen through the fact that the first chapter of *Propaganda* itself is titled “Organizing Chaos”.

²¹ This text offers both a forceful defense of American-style democracy and a call to mobilise public opinion behind it. Yet this book itself functions as a form of propaganda, defining and promoting a particular vision of “democracy” as necessary and normatively superior. Here, Bernays makes it “common sense” that democracy’s value lies in rationality and order over irrationality and destruction. (Tye, 1998, pp.103-126).

what he terms “our modern mass society.” His approach to public opinion rests on a notably pessimistic view of the average person’s capacity for independent thought. In *Propaganda*, he frequently depicts the masses as a “herd” that responds more to symbols and subconscious stimuli²² than to rational argument (Ewen, 1996). As he states, “Men are rarely aware of the real reasons which motivate their actions, [...]” (Bernays, 1928, p.55). From this assumption of mass irrationality follows the notion that the public should remain largely passive (Ewen, 1996). He bluntly asks, “If we understand the mechanism and motives of the group mind, is it not possible to control and regiment the masses according to our will without their knowing it?” (Bernays, 1928, p.71). This rhetorical flourish presumes both the right and the power of invisible governors to do precisely that.

Thus, large swaths of people can be “swung” with minimal effort. Gramsci, by contrast, aims to confront this unconscious “consent” through “intellectual and moral reform” (Gramsci, 1971, p.133), asserting that crises or transformations are possible only if subordinate classes develop their own intellectuals (Gramsci, 1971, pp.9–11). Bernays’s design, however, leaves scant room for such bottom-up challenges. He regards mass democracy as precarious, stabilised through an “invisible government” orchestrating popular sentiment (Bernays, 1928, p.38). Ordinary citizens do not deliberate; they respond to top-down emotional management, and without it, “[...] they would find it impossible to come to a conclusion about anything” (Bernays, 1928, pp.10–11).

In summary, Bernays’ framework reduces democracy to a carefully calibrated spectacle. By diagnosing the public as incurably irrational, he legitimates the paternal rule of self-styled experts – an invisible government that channels mass impulses for desired ends. When measured against Gramsci’s hope of bottom-up intellectual leadership, Bernays’s approach appears to invert that logic: it denies the potential for genuine participation in favor of top-down “management.” Chapter 3 will probe this tension more systematically, asking whether Bernays’s “engineering of consent” can be squared with any robust notion of democracy—or if it must be seen, as Gramsci might insist, as a subtle apparatus of hegemony that bars real social transformation.

3 Gramsci vs. Bernays - Public Opinion and the “possibility” of change

The two authors agree in their recognition of power’s reliance on consent in modern societies, as was made clear in chapters 1.1 and 2.1 of this thesis. Nonetheless, their theories diverge sharply when it comes to the origins, mechanisms, and implications of consent. They arrive at ultimately different visions of democracy. These will now be compared, starting with a comparison of their

²² While Lippmann viewed “pseudo-environments” and stereotypes as distortions that imperil democratic accuracy, Bernays recast them as strategic levers for guiding a passive public, thus rebranding Lippmann’s cautionary stance into an endorsement of top-down consent engineering.

diagnosis of social reality and, finally, a conclusion revolving around the two authors' seemingly paradoxical visions for democracy.

3.1 Bottom-up Empowerment vs. Top-Down Management

3.1.1 The Nature of Consent

Although the two authors draw starkly different conclusions from the conviction that consent is manufactured, certain similarities are worth noting. Both authors recognise that mass consent is a systematic, mostly invisible force that maintains social order, especially in times of stability²³. While Gramsci sees hegemonic consent as a fragile, negotiated acceptance of a dominant worldview, Bernays states openly that democracy necessitates the “[...] conscious and intelligent manipulation of the organized habits and opinions of the masses” by an elite minority (Bernays, 1928, p. 37). His notion of consent portrays managed consent as not only benign but necessary for “[...] a smoothly functioning society [...]” (Bernays, 1928, p.9).

This “smoothness” is neither a realistic nor desirable characteristic of consent according to Gramsci, as what appears as public agreement is, in fact, a “spontaneous consent” that the ruling class must continuously secure through ideological leadership. Far from being the quiet achievement of a hidden hand, consent for Gramsci is the site of an ongoing struggle between competing hegemony – “historically” caused and always subject to erosion when societal contradictions intensify. In Gramsci’s paradigm, hegemony is never total; it is “protected by the armour of coercion”²⁴, meaning the state’s apparatus of force stands ready for moments when consent breaks down (1971, p.263).

Unlike Bernays’s celebration of organised agreement, Gramsci argues that unconscious consent by the public is problematic precisely because it prevents critical consciousness and meaningful change (Fontana, 2006). This lays bare a contradiction at the heart of liberal democracy: while claiming to reflect the people’s will, it systematically shapes and limits that will through ideological dominance. Thus, whereas Bernays sees *managed* consent as essential for stability, Gramsci views *authentic* consent as an unstable and contestable condition crucial for true democratic vitality.

3.1.2 The Role of the Public

Following their differing conceptions of consent, the role of the public is conceived in almost inverse ways by the two thinkers. Bernays assumes the public is “[...] driven by instincts and

²³ For Gramsci, the purpose and function of democracy is seen as a dynamic process in which hegemonic stability is challenged in times of crisis, while for Bernays, consent is something to be skillfully upheld.

²⁴ “[...] in the sense that one might say that State = political society + civil society, in other words hegemony protected by the armour of coercion.” (Gramsci, 1971, p.263).

emotions rather than reason”; left to their own devices, the masses would make chaotic, ill-informed choices that could imperil social order. Here, however, one might well ask: if “[...] the basic elements of human nature are fixed as to desires and instincts [...]” (Bernays, 1923, p.150), why assume only the masses, and not the elites, remain subject to these same chaotic impulses?

Gramsci argues that both everyday people and intellectuals unconsciously absorb “common sense” tainted by historical class relations²⁵, rather than the public voluntarily or subconsciously taking on a passive role under the elite’s conscious shaping of the world. Bernays justifies this passive role by claiming that the average citizen is incapable of “rational” self-decision and is swayed by “emotions” (1928, pp. 38-40). Rather than denying this inherent emotional quality of man or trying to resolve it, Gramsci radically points to the error of neglecting its value:

“The popular element²⁶ ‘feels’ but does not always *know* or understand; the intellectual element ‘knows’ but does not always understand and in particular does not always *feel*. [...] The intellectual’s error consists in believing that one can know without understanding and more without *feeling* and being impassioned.” (Gramsci, 1971, p.418, emphasis added)

That most people feel but do not “understand or know fully” need not point toward “herd” mediocracy as is with Bernays; rather, it is precisely out of this ability to “feel” that political history arises. To Gramsci, emotions and values themselves are part of what can mobilise the public as agents: outrage at injustice, hope for a better future, solidarity with others—these feelings can be harnessed in a constructive, consciousness-raising project (Gramsci, 1971, p. 419). In Gramsci’s paradigm, the public is the *protagonist* in waiting - the sleeping giant that can awaken²⁷. He envisions a public that can evolve from passive to active, given the development of critical awareness as well as “organic intellectuals” helping articulate the subordinate group’s experiences and aspirations – who themselves come from no other than the classes that they represent (Gramsci, 1971, p. 5).

Bluntly accepting the social reality where contesting ideas permeate civil society, Gramsci assigns human agency to the public, calling upon each new social class and its “organic intellectuals” to translate into counter-hegemonic narratives. It is the passive acceptance of “common sense” that Bernays prescribes as a role of the masses, not the inherent “emotional” nature that makes them unworthy to rule, that blinds both the masses and the intellectuals in normal times.

²⁵ The causes for the public’s agreement with “common sense” also differ for the two authors. It is not the public’s irrationality or susceptibility to cleverly orchestrated propaganda, but historical path dependencies, which makes it difficult to challenge “common sense”. See: Gramsci, 1971, pp.145-147.

²⁶ Gramsci addresses popular and intellectual “elements” within each person, rather than classifying individuals into rational and intellectual elites who think and the herd that merely feels.

²⁷ Note that the word “awaken” as opposed to “be awoken” is used. Gramsci’s public is, at least potentially, an active historical subject - once they awaken their collective power (1971, p.9). Even though the masses may at times be subdued by prevailing ideology, Gramsci insists they are capable of developing their own critical consciousness and leadership.

Whether the public is seen as an audience or a protagonist leads ultimately to the most significant divergence between the two authors: their visions of democracy.

3.2 Minimalist vs. Radical²⁸ Democracy

Nowhere is the contrast between Gramsci and Bernays clearer than in their visions of democracy itself. The fact that both authors recognise the pervasiveness of engineered public opinion in liberal democracy does not hide the fact that a considerable difference can also be observed here concerning its implications for democracy: Bernays acknowledges that modern democracies are governed by an “invisible government” – the “will of the people” is less a genuine aggregate of independent views and more a reflection of what leaders have led the people to believe. A similar sobriety regarding the depth of indoctrination in sustaining the status quo can be found in Gramsci, but the authors diverge in their attitudes towards the role of the public in challenging managed consent in democracy – both in the *possibility* and the *desirability* of it.

Bernays does not view “organised” consent as a betrayal of democracy but as its *salvation* – he sees it as a tool of “[...] killing democracy²⁹ in order to save it, [...]” from the danger posed by the emotionally impulsive and irrational qualities of the masses (Olasky, 1985, p.191, Tye, 1998). Hence, Bernays is “[...] a pessimist because of intelligence [...]” (Gramsci, 1994, p.175). The propaganda of the “self-perpetuating elite” serves a function analogous to how Gramsci’s “traditional intellectuals”³⁰ perpetuate class distinctions, but it is devoted to democracy rather than exploitative of it. Democracy, for Bernays, becomes a kind of *guided equilibrium*: so long as the populace is content – or at least pliant – under the influence of propaganda, democratic society is stable and *therefore* successful. This minimalist vision reduces public participation to endorsement and leadership selection, leaving the shaping of consent to a few (Schumpeter, 1942). Meanwhile, Gramsci states in his rare discussion of democracy in *Prison Notebooks*:

²⁸ Laclau and Mouffe (1985) further developed Gramsci’s dialectical concept of hegemony into a broader strategy of radical democracy. They extend Gramsci’s notion of ideological contestation beyond the economic-class terrain to embrace multiple forms of social antagonism—including feminist, ecological, anti-racist, and LGBTQ+ struggles—thus democratising Gramsci’s original Marxist framework.

²⁹ Bernays conceded that democracy would not be a free marketplace of ideas, but he believed that was a fair trade-off to prevent disorder or the rise of extremist movements (Olasky, 1985).

³⁰ It is then not surprising that some scholars continue to portray Gramsci as an elitist vanguardist (Reed, 2012; Hill, 2007). However, while the social function that Bernays’s “PR specialists” and Gramsci’s “traditional intellectuals” carry out are analogous, the origins and implications of their prestige are significantly different – Gramsci emphasises historical class relations and structural factors, while Bernays emphasises professional training and individual factors that distinguish specialists from the masses.

“Democracy [...] must mean that **every** ‘citizen’ can ‘govern’ and that society places him, even if only abstractly, in a general condition to achieve this. Political democracy tends towards a **coincidence of the rulers and the ruled** [...] ensuring for each non-ruler a **free training** in the skills [...] necessary to that end.” (Gramsci, 1971, pp. 40-41, emphasis added)

Thus, in Gramsci’s view, it does not suffice that the public simply “agrees” to the intellectuals; they must potentially contribute themselves to shaping consent. Despite the lack of an explicit discussion of democracy³¹ in Gramsci’s writings, his theory of civil society implicitly points toward a more radical, participatory vision (Buttigieg, 1995; Laclau & Mouffe, 2014). The minimalist democracy that Bernays proposes is seen by Gramsci as one historically contingent formation of power – namely, bourgeoisie hegemony – rather than a true democracy of representation (Morera, 1990; Zemblyas, 2022; Buttigieg, 1995). Gramsci pointedly refuses to define democracy by its manipulative conditions alone. He portrays hegemony and counter-hegemony as a dialectical process, where leadership by consent is always balanced against the possibility of resistance.³² As Laclau & Mouffe(2014) note, Gramsci perceives the potential disruption of hegemony as a democratic necessity: democracy's vitality resides in its inherent instability, its openness to contestation, and its capacity for empowering public participation. Democratic life, for Gramsci, is and should inherently be a *struggle* – a bottom-up negotiation among classes and groups.

These opposed conceptions of democracy correspond to fundamentally different stances on mass psychology – particularly the role of irrationality and emotion in public life. Bernays’s justification of rule by elites – the danger³³ of mass emotions and irrationality – is the very point where Gramsci sees his optimistic vision of challenging “common sense”.³⁴ Gramsci points out:

“The intellectual’s error consists in believing that one can know without understanding and without feeling and being impassioned. [...] the relations between the intellectual and the people-nation are, or are reduced to, relationships of a purely bureaucratic and formal order; the intellectuals become a caste [...]” (Gramsci, 1971, pp.418-419)

While Bernays’s intellectuals employ “[...] as nearly scientific an analysis as possible [...]” (Bernays, 1928, p.97), Gramsci’s “organic” intellectuals unite cold critical insight with fiery passion. He argues that a true democratic movement must engage people at the level of heart as well as mind.

³¹ In *Prison Notebooks*, Gramsci’s discussion of democracy is focused on diagnosing historical and contemporary instances of it, rather than envisioning a future for democracy as a main theme. That being said, Gramsci’s discussion of civil society reveals his democratic visions, which is more “socialist” and “radical” than “liberal”, with democracy as a system that allows for socialism, which is his primary focus(Buttigieg, 1995).

³² As Femia (1975) observes, Gramsci’s approach thus “avoids the shortcomings of both the consensus and conflict schools of modern social theory,” recognizing that society is neither purely harmonious nor purely coercive; it is integrated by a blend of voluntary acceptance and structural compulsion, each of which can be reconfigured by human agency (pp. 47–48).

³³ Influenced by Gustave Le Bon’s theory of the herd instinct and by Freud’s insights into unconscious drives, Bernays believed that society left to its own passions would be “irrational and dangerous” (Olasky, 1985).

³⁴ He insists against Bernays’s deterministic pessimism that although manipulation and passivity may be prevalent during “normal” times, they must never become democracy’s defining characteristic.

Indeed, for Gramsci, emotion and democratic awakening are inextricably linked: his democratic vision lies in elevating and channelling collective class emotions through democratic education and participation, converting raw passion into an organized will for change (Pateman, 1970; Simon, 1982;). That is to say, Gramsci's progressive, democratic vision of society empowers the bottom to affect the top.

In essence, Bernays privileges stability and a more "minimalist" democracy (Schumpeter, 1942; Przeworski, 1999) in which elites guide mass opinion for the sake of social order, whereas Gramsci envisions a more "radical" democracy (Mouffe, 1979; Morera, 1990; Laclau & Mouffe, 2014), one driven by bottom-up participation and the possibility of challenging hegemony. Neither approach is definitively "better" or "worse"; they simply reflect two distinct logics of how a modern mass democracy might be organised—one prioritising orderly management, the other embracing popular contestation. Which is more widely accepted as a "common sense" ideal of democracy is a matter of hegemony and propaganda in itself.

Conclusion

This paper has placed the theories of Antonio Gramsci and Edward L. Bernays at the center of an inquiry into democratic consent, highlighting how public opinion can either sustain a minimal democracy that keeps power unchallenged or become a catalyst for radical democracy that strives to redistribute power. While both thinkers recognise that public opinion is organised rather than spontaneously generated, they diverge significantly in their democratic visions and the role they assign to consent.

Gramsci frames hegemony as a structural force in liberal democracy that, although powerful, can be contested. He claims that social change is "possible" – though not inevitable – if the public, guided by "organic intellectuals," develops critical consciousness to challenge dominant ideologies. On the other hand, Bernays conceives of propaganda as a practical means to safeguard democracy from its own potential instability, essentially managing public opinion through top-down persuasion. For him, the public is prone to emotional impulses and thus benefits from the propaganda of expert strategists. That said, Bernays and Gramsci fundamentally diverge on whether consent can and should – at least potentially – be questioned and contested by the citizens.

Another key point of distinction emerges in how each thinker views intellectuals. Whereas Bernays underscores the necessity of a small, capable elite to stabilise society, Gramsci pictures intellectuals springing from within the masses to question and reshape the prevailing order. These varying roles mirror broader differences in their conceptions of democracy: Bernays's paternalistic model manages and stabilises the masses, whereas Gramsci's radical model underscores participation, bottom-up empowerment, and an ongoing struggle for more inclusive forms of

governance.

As a final point of comparison, this paper examined the public's political agency to highlight the authors' implicit democratic visions. Bernays portrays the public as largely incapable of self-direction, requiring guidance from those adept at persuasion. Gramsci contends that the masses can cultivate critical awareness through counter-hegemonic efforts and collective organization. What Bernays would label mass irrationality, Gramsci recasts as collective enthusiasm, a necessary ingredient for forging a "national-popular" will among the oppressed. Where Gramsci seeks to empower the people to shape their own history, Bernays refines how their perceptions can be shaped for them by certain intellectuals to prevent chaos.

Comparing their ideas brings into focus a core tension in liberal democracy: Is democracy primarily a mechanism to maintain stability or a stepping-stone toward more inclusive political participation? On one side lies a paternalistic approach that keeps democracy orderly through guided persuasion; on the other, a radical vision in which democracy evolves through sustained contestation and grassroots empowerment. This divergence not only illuminates the deeper forces at play in modern democracy but also underscores how the very *content* of "democracy" is not fixed but open to strategic manipulation or transformative contestation. In this sense, the perspectives of Gramsci and Bernays remain profoundly relevant, revealing how democracy's ideals and practices are continually forged in the interplay of *hegemony* and *propaganda*.

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